

seasons. Spikelet fertility for each plant was evaluated visually. Varieties showing more than 80% spikelet fertility were classified as restorers, those showing 10-79% fertility as partial restorers, and those with less OM88 and IR28228-12-3-1-3 were suspected maintainers for IR46830A and IR54752A, respectively.

The effectivity of maintainers will be confirmed by backcrossing and scoring individual plants of BC progenies for pollen sterility. Completely pollen sterile BC progenies would indicate that the suspected maintainer is effective, and could be converted that into a CMS line. □

Restorers and maintainers for male sterile lines identified at CLRRRI, Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam, 1987-89 dry and wet seasons.

Male sterile line	Fertility restorer lines	Partial restorer lines	Suspected maintainer lines
IR46829A	NN3A, NN4B	IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	OM88
IR46830A	NN3A, OM576 IR66, IR29723-143-3-2-2-1	OM86-9, ITA212 IR64,OM80 IR28228-12-3-1-1-2	OM88
IR48483A	OM86-9, OM90, IR54 IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 IR31801-124-1-3	NN7A IR28228-12-3-1-1-2	IR31917-45-3-2-2
IR54752A	IR64, OM80, OM576 NN4B, NN5B, IR54 IR29723-143-3-2-1	ITA212 IR27316-60-3-2-2	IR28228-12-3-1-1-2

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Breeding methods—tissue culture

D₂₀₂₆, a promising rice dwarf mutant of Guangluai 4

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We irradiated seeds of Guangluai 4, a short-duration local rice variety with high yield and wide adaptability, with ⁶⁰Co r-rays (30 kR) + Ar⁺Laser (80 J/cm²).

Starting with the M₂, plants were selected for dwarf stature. Mutant D₂₀₂₆, selected in the M₄, has significantly shorter plants, shorter panicles, and lower 1,000-grain weight than Guangluai 4 (see table). But it has higher seed-setting.

The mutant has a good plant type with plant height of 46.2-58.4 cm. It should be a good source of the dwarf character in breeding projects. □

Agronomic characters of the dwarf mutant D₂₀₂₆ and its mother variety Guangluai 4. Hunan, China, 1988.

Characteristic	Mutant D ₂₀₂₆	Guangluai 4
Plant height (cm)	52.3	74.3
Panicle length (cm)	15.2	19.6
Seed-setting rate (%)	85.9	81.8
1,000-grain weight (g)	17.9	23.8
Yield per plant (g)	8.3	16.4

Decline of morphogenic potential in microspore-derived calli from indica/japonica and japonica/japonica F₁ hybrids

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In large-scale anther culture plant production, the callus transfer activity consumes time, medium, and space.

Hence, it is more efficient to concentrate on cultures possessing good morphogenic potential.

Rice anthers inoculated onto a semisolid induction medium produce visible microspore-derived calli from 4 to 10 wk after inoculation, in an asynchronous callus induction process. Transferring calli to the regeneration medium when they are 1-2 mm in size ensures better regeneration efficiency. But that requires repeated callus transfers.

Green plant regenerating ability (GPRA) of microspore-derived calli as a function of time when calli attained transferable stage, IIRI. 1989. Each liter of the callus-inducing medium (N6AK) = N6 basal salts, Fe source, and vitamins supplemented with 2 mg naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), 0.5 mg kinetin, 60 g sucrose, and 5.5 g agarose; each liter of the regeneration medium (R6) = N6 basal salts, Fe source, and vitamins supplemented with 1 mg kinetin and 0.1 mg naphthalene acetic acid, 40 g sucrose, and 5.5 g agarose.